

Financial Management Practices Applied by Principals for Administrative Effectiveness in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

Chukwuogo, Nkiruka Hope (Ph.D)
Department of Educational Management and Policy
Faculty of Education,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka

Abstract

The study investigated financial management practices applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 538 respondents (269 principals and 269 bursars) in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Census sampling technique was used since the entire 538 were studied because it is relatively small and manageable. The researcher developed questionnaire namely ‘‘Principals’ Financial Management Practices for Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire (PFMPAEQ)’’ was used for data collection. The face validation of the instrument was determined by three experts of which two were from the Department of Educational Management and Policy, and one in Measurement and Evaluation Unit in the Department of Educational Foundations, all from Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Cronbach alpha method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument which yielded overall coefficient of 0.82. The researcher together with five research assistants collected data for the study using the direct approach method and 99% return was recorded. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while t-test was used to test the hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed among others that budgeting practices are applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Also, there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and bursars on auditing practices applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that Ministry of Education should develop standard manual to serve as guideline to principals in engaging in auditing practices for enhancing their administrative effectiveness in secondary schools.

Keywords: Financial Management, Principals, Administrative Effectiveness, Budgeting, Auditing

Introduction

Principals play substantial roles in bringing about success and development of secondary education institutions of learning. It is the principals that plan, organize and control the use of available resources to achieve set goals in secondary schools. Principals as described by Nnebedum, Oshia, Nwanne and Chinagorom (2022), are the chief administrators and leaders who plan, coordinate, control and motivate staff to ensure smooth operation of secondary schools. One of the significant expectations from principals is to utilize financial, time, material and human resources to achieve sets goals and objectives of learning institutions. The attainment of predetermined goals and objectives is associated with administrative effectiveness.

Administrative effectiveness is state of being successful in organizing activities and implementing programmes of an institution to attain predetermined goals. Obiekezie and Obi (2025) defined administrative effectiveness as the ability of principals to achieve the educational goals of secondary schools through their managerial prowess. The notion of administrative effectiveness is to ensure well-functioning of the daily affairs of secondary schools for actualization of predetermined goals. Administrative effectiveness is described by Idowu and Akeredolu (2025), as performing a programme or carry out an activity or operation according to the goals of the organization. Operationally, Administrative effectiveness is the efficacy of principals in planning, mobilizing and utilizing the available resources to realize set goals.

There are many managerial activities that could be used to assess administrative effectiveness of principals. Faruk and Ajadi, (2023) noted administrative effectiveness of principals is measured by how appreciable students' academic performance obtained in both internal and external examinations, the level of adherence of both the learners and the staff to the rules and regulations of the schools, the level of judicious utilization of the school facilities, the level of teachers' dedication to their duties, ability of the school managers to provide a sense of direction as the head, the level of internal supervision carried out in schools and a host of others. The level of administrative effectiveness of principals is determined through their managerial activities such as planning activities, decision-making, delegation of duties, communication, supervision, conflict resolution, financial and record management among others. In the same vein, Nebo and Afianmagbon (2025) asserted that administrative effectiveness of principals could be assessed through task areas which typically include instructional leadership, staff supervision, student discipline, school finance management, communication and community relations, curriculum implementation, and general school governance.

The existence of some problems could be associated with administrative ineffectiveness of some principals in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Ofojebe and Ikegbunam (2020) observed administrative ineffectiveness of secondary schools in Anambra State which is connected with teachers' inefficiency and poor job commitment, inconsistency of school supervision, examination malpractice, indiscipline among teachers and students, school administrators' poor accountability, inadequate community involvement in schools among others. Some of these problems in secondary schools are directly or indirectly associated with financial management practices of principals as funds are essential for running the daily activities of learning institutions.

Financial management practices are the strategic approaches to planning, sourcing, mobilizing, utilizing and accounting for funds expended in operating daily activities of an institution. According to Onyali, Ogbo and Uwaezuoke (2023), financial management practices are the systematic ways of handling monetary transactions in the school system by the principals. Financial management practices are measures to ensure prudence in the use of scarce funds in the implementation of programmes in learning institutions. Financial management practices as defined by Obi and Michael (2024), are decisions on the way to procure; expend and provides an account of the fund provided for the implementation of organizational programmes. Contextually, financial management practices are activities and techniques that ensure funds are well-sourced and appropriately allocated, established procedures are followed in spending, expenditure are recorded accurately and explanation provided on how funds are used in running the daily affairs of secondary schools. Mabi and Buluma (2024) listed financial management practices as follow: budgeting, auditing and financial internal controls. The focus of this study is on budgeting and auditing practices as they are the core mechanisms for managing school funds.

Budgeting is the act of developing blue print of anticipated income and expenditure of the school in a given fiscal year. According to Obi and Michael (2024), budgeting is a guideline or blueprint of all expected revenue generation sources and particulars expected to expend within a specified period in the future. Budgeting involves developing financial activities and programmes for attaining set goals and objectives of secondary schools. It is the means of expressing school programmes in monetary terms at given period. Budgeting practices are procedures for estimation of income and expenditure to ensure efficient financial resource allocation over a specific period in an organization. Oyeniran, Adebayo, Olayinka and Tumburku (2025) described budgeting practices as the processes of compiling past financial experiences, outlining current plans, and projecting future financial needs over a set timeframe. Continuing, Oyeniran stated that budgeting practices encompasses planning, allocation, and monitoring of funds which is crucial for improving academic outcomes, maintaining infrastructure, and supporting staff development. Budgeting practices are means of developing guidelines for use of financial uses to avoid unnecessary spending and minimize misappropriation of funds in secondary schools. This is

expatiated by Musa and Kaugama (2025) who maintained that budgeting practices prevent wastages or reckless spending of funds provided for various educational services because the operators of budget are compelled to follow the appropriate estimate in spending funds.

Auditing is the process of reviewing and scrutinizing financial records and activities of an organization. According to Egboka and Okoye (2024), auditing is a deliberate and careful way of accessing financial statements in the school. Continuing, Egboka and Okoye (2024) maintained that audit report on a financial statement reflects a true and fair view of the school's affairs which may include school administrators spending habit and that of other staff delegated to do so. Auditing practices are structured approaches and techniques for examining financial documents to verify their accuracy and reliability in organization. Mohamed and Chui (2023) noted that auditing practices enable principals to identify and rectify financial irregularities, enhance transparency, and ensure compliance with financial policies and regulations. It is through auditing practices that school managers can find out, if their financial records are free from errors or frauds. Okeke and Okaforcha (2020) expatiated that auditing practices help in examining various school accounting books, ascertaining the degree of adherence to budgetary guidelines and finding out the level of integrity of the key financial managers in the school through cash survey and also checking of school cash books and revenue collected.

There are cases of misplacement of priorities and wastages of funds in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Thompson, Mmaduabuchi, Oparaji and Chukwuemeka-Nworu (2024) noted that some principals often face allegations of financial mismanagement, lack of initiative in seeking alternative funding, budget negligence, inefficient fund disbursement in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Michael. Amaefula and Chukwu (2024) averred that poor financial management practices gave rise to various critical issues that hinder effective administration of public secondary schools in Anambra State. Furthermore, Michael et al asserted that lack of transparency and accountability in financial practices foster corruption and embezzlement which drain resources intended for enhance teaching and learning in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Also, Egboka and Okoye (2024) asserted that the alleged act of financial mismanagement, misappropriation and embezzlement by some principals could partly contribute to the poor condition of infrastructural facilities like furniture, generating sets, motor vehicles, and maintenance of teaching/learning materials such as computer systems, science laboratory materials among others in some public secondary schools in Anambra State. It is in the light of these problems that the study investigated financial management practices applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

Received: 15 May 2025

Revised: 20 May 2025

Accepted: 25 May 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

644

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15534481>

The main purpose of the study is to investigate financial management practices applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to investigate:

1. Budgeting practices applied by principals for administrative effectiveness public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Auditing practices applied by principals for administrative effectiveness public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the budgeting practices applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What are the auditing practices applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of principals and bursars on the budgeting practices applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of principals and bursars on the auditing practices applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Methods

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study comprised 538 respondents (269 principals and 269 bursars) in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Census or total sampling technique was used since the entire population is relatively small and manageable. Therefore, the 269 principals and 269 bursars in public secondary school in Anambra State were utilized for the study.

A researcher-developed instruments titled “Principals’ Financial Management Practices for Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire (PFMPAEQ)” was used for data collection. The instruments were developed by the researcher based on review of related literature and consultation of experts in educational management. PFMPAEQ had Cluster A and B which were based on the two components of financial management practices adopted in the study. Cluster A had eight items which focused on budgeting practices and Cluster B which centred on auditing practices had seven

items. PFMPAEQ contained 15 items structured on a four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The instrument was subjected to face and content validation by three experts, two in the Department of Educational Management and Policy, and one in the Department of Educational Foundations, all in the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Cronbach alpha was used to establish the reliability of the instrument which yielded co-efficient values of 0.84 and 0.80 for the two clusters of PFMPAEQ with an overall coefficient value of 0.82.

The researcher together with five research assistants who are secondary school teachers in the area of study administered copies of the questionnaires directly to the respondents. A total of 538 copies of the instruments were distributed and 530 copies of questionnaires were properly filled and successfully retrieved, indicating 99 percent return rate. At the end of the exercise, duly completed and retrieved copies of the instruments were used for data analysis. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while t-test was used to test the hypotheses. The decision criteria for the research questions is that any mean rating of 2.50 and above was considered as agreement and any mean rating of below 2.50 was considered as disagreement. In taking decisions on the null hypotheses, if the exact p-value is equal to or greater than significant value of 0.05, the null hypothesis was not rejected but if exact p-value is less than significant value of 0.05, the null hypotheses was rejected.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the budgeting practices applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

S/N	ITEMS	Principals (N =265)			Bursars (N =265)		
		Mean	SD	Decision	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Set up budget planning committee	2.68	1.02	Agree	2.62	1.07	Agree
2	Forecast the expected income for a given fiscal year	2.81	1.10	Agree	2.76	1.11	Agree
3	Estimate anticipated expenditure of a given fiscal year	2.59	1.05	Agree	2.60	0.98	Agree
4	Prioritize pressing needs in planning allocation of funds	2.63	1.11	Agree	2.55	1.08	Agree
5	Adhere to government policy on drafting budget	2.60	1.09	Agree	2.67	1.12	Agree
6	Ensure approval of proposed budget before implementation						
7	Adhere to budgetary provisions in allocation of resources to various units	2.47	0.96	Disagree	2.41	1.10	Disagree
8	Engage in continuous monitoring of the progress in the implementation of school budget	2.58	1.00	Agree	2.53	1.03	Agree

Mean of Means	2.62	1.05	Agree	2.59	1.07	Agree
----------------------	-------------	-------------	--------------	-------------	-------------	--------------

Table 1: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation Scores of Principals and Bursars on Budgeting Practices Applied by Principals for Administrative Effectiveness in Public Secondary Schools
 Table 1 reveals the mean scores of both principals and bursars for all items with exception of item 7 are above cut off mean score of 2.50 and this indicated agreement with the items as the budgeting practices applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools. The overall standard deviation scores for principal and bursars which stand at 1.05 and 1.07 respectively indicate homogeneity in their mean scores. The cluster mean of 2.62 for principals and 2.59 for bursars are above 2.50 indicating that budgeting practices are applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 2: What are the auditing practices applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation Scores of Principals and Bursars on Auditing Practices Applied by Principals for Administrative Effectiveness in Public Secondary Schools

S/N	ITEMS	Principals (N =265)			Bursars (N =265)		
		Mean	SD	Decision	Mean	SD	Decision
9	Set up audit committee	2.42	1.07	Disagree	2.37	1.06	Disagree
10	Set regulations that guide auditing	2.41	1.10	Disagree	2.42	1.04	Disagree
11	Set aside specific period of the year for conducting auditing	2.58	1.09	Agree	2.54	1.00	Agree
12	Involve stakeholders in the auditing process to enhance transparency	2.41	1.06	Disagree	2.45	1.00	Disagree
13	Adhere to government policy on internal auditing	2.47	1.12	Disagree	2.44	1.03	Disagree
14	Make available essential financial records to aid auditing	2.54	1.06	Agree	2.52	1.11	Agree
15	Give annual auditing report	2.52	0.99	Agree	2.50	1.08	Agree
	Mean of Means	2.48	1.07	Disagree	2.46	1.05	Disagree

Premised on data analysis presented on table 2, both principals and bursars disagreed on items 9,10, 12 and 13 as the auditing practices adopted by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools and this is shown by their mean scores of the items that are below the cut-off mean of 2.50. The mean scores of both principals and bursars for all items 11, 14 and 15 are above cut off mean score of 2.50 and this indicated agreement with the items as the auditing practices applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools. The overall standard deviation scores for principals and bursars which stand at 1.07 and 1.05 respectively indicate convergence of their responses implying that their responses are homogenous. The cluster mean of 2.48 for principals and 2.46 bursars are below 2.50 indicating

auditing practices are not applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of principals and bursars on the budgeting practices applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 3: The Summary of t-test of Significant Difference Between the Mean Ratings of Principals and Bursars on Budgeting Practices Applied by Principals for Administrative Effectiveness in Public Secondary Schools

Respondents	N	X	SD	p-value	∞	Df	Remark
Principals	265	2.62	1.05	0.26	0.05	528	Not Significant
Bursars	265	2.59	1.07				

Result in Table 3 shows that the p-value of 0.26 is greater than 0.05 level of significance at 528 degree of freedom. Thus, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between the groups was not rejected. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of principals and bursars on the budgeting practices applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of principals and bursars on the auditing practices applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: The Summary of t-test of Significant Difference Between the Mean Ratings of Principals and Bursars on Auditing Practices Applied by Principals for Administrative Effectiveness in Public Secondary Schools

Respondents	N	X	SD	p-value	∞	Df	Remark
Principals	265	2.48	1.07	0.26	0.05	528	Not Significant
Bursars	265	2.46	1.05				

As shown in Table 4 shows that the p-value of 0.26 is greater than 0.05 level of significance at 528 degree of freedom. Thus, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between the groups was not rejected. This is an indication that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of principals and bursars on the auditing practices applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Discussion

Received: 15 May 2025

Revised: 20 May 2025

Accepted: 25 May 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

The finding of the study revealed that budgeting practices are applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This agreed with the finding of Oyeniran, Adebayo, Olayinka and Tumburku (2025) which indicated that principal budgeting management practices were employed by the secondary school principals. The agreement in finding could be explained by similarity in budgeting policy across the country in which the studies were conducted. This refuted the finding of Njini et al (2025) who reported that budgeting practices were low in secondary schools. The disagreement between the findings could be attributed difference in geographical locations of the studies which could have varying policies guiding budgeting practices. The budgeting practices applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State were to set up budget planning committee, forecast the expected income for a given fiscal year, estimate anticipated expenditure of a given fiscal year, prioritize pressing needs in planning allocation of funds, ensure approval of proposed budget before implementation and engage in continuous monitoring of the progress in the implementation of school budget. The principals apply budgeting practices are properly plan and control the use of limited funds to enhance administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The budgeting practice applied are instrumental to prevention of under and over-spending of funds in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It was also found that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of principals and bursars on the budgeting practices applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This upheld the finding of Obi and Michael (2024) which showed that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of Principals and Bursars on the budgeting practices adopted by principals for effective administration of secondary schools.

The result of the study auditing practices are not applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This affirmed the finding of Okeze, Okpe and Ngwakwe (2018) which revealed that auditing practices were not adopted in public secondary schools. The similarity in educational level and geopolitical zone in Nigeria in which the studies were conducted could contribute to the agreement between the findings. This disagreed with the finding Mohamed and Chui (2023) which indicated that principals engage in auditing practices in financial management in public secondary schools. The possible reason for the disagreement in findings is that the studies were conducted in different countries within varying policies guiding auditing practices of principals in secondary schools. The auditing practices are not applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State were setting up audit committee, setting regulations that guide auditing, involving stakeholders in the auditing process to enhance transparency and adhering to government policy on internal auditing. Auditing practices are not applied by principals probably due to their incompetency in carrying their exercise in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The failure of principals to apply auditing practices have undermined transparency and accountability in

public secondary schools in Anambra State. Further result indicated that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of principals and bursars on the auditing practices applied by principals for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This supported the finding of Okeze, Okpe and Ngwakwe (2018) which showed that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of principals and bursars on auditing practices of secondary schools.

Conclusion

Based on the findings it was concluded that principals are yet to fully apply financial management for administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Therefore, funds made available to principals in running daily activities are yet fully utilized to enhance administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made from the findings of this study:

1. Principals should improve on their budgeting practices by adhering to budgetary provisions in allocation of resources to various units in schools.
2. Ministry of Education should develop standard manual to serve as guideline to principals in engaging in auditing practices for enhancing their administrative effectiveness in secondary schools.

REFERENCES

- Egboka, P.N. and Okoye, U.T. (2024). Comparative analysis of principals' cost management practices for administrative effectiveness of public and private secondary schools in Awka Education Zone. *Unizik Journal of Educational Management and Policy*, 6(2), 53-58.
- Faruk, Y.A., & Ajadi, T.A. (2023). School environments and principals' administrative effectiveness in Kwara State public secondary schools, Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Education Humanities and Commerce*, 4(3), 51-58.
- Idowu, E.K., & Akeredolu, S.A. (2025). Principal administrative effectiveness and teachers' job productivity in Secondary schools in Ekiti State. *IJO International Journal of Educational Research*, 8(3), 40-50.
- Mabi, J., & Buluma, A. (2024). A systematic review of the effect of financial management practices on service delivery in secondary schools. *Journal of Effective Teaching Methods*, 2(4), 28-43.

- Michael. K.C., Amaefula, F.N., & Chukwu, R.N. (2024). Relationship between financial management practices and effective administrative of secondary schools in Anambra State. *African Journal of Educational Management, Teaching and Entrepreneurship Studies*, 12(1), 176-183.
- Mohamed, A.A., & Chui, M.M. (2023). Influence of principals' auditing practices on financial management in public secondary schools in Mandera West Sub-County, Mandera County, Kenya. *African Journal of Emerging Issues*, 5(5), 49-61.
- Musa, M., & Kaugama, H. H. (2025). Assessment of the impacts of budgeting on the development of higher schools in Jigawa State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and National Development*, 3(1), 55-60. Available at DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14924009
- Nebo, C.L., & Afianmagbon, B.E. (2025). Principals' task areas and administrative effectiveness in missionary secondary schools: A study of South-East Nigerian States. *Iconic Research and Engineering Journals*, 8(10), 905-918.
- Njini, S., Moyo, A., Guvhu, R., Matope, N., Mugadza, A. T., Murewi, C.T.F., Dambaza, M., Mugodzwa, T.T., & Mawere, D. (2025). An Analysis of the state of budgeting at school level in one selected District in Zimbabwe. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 13(1), 289-306. Available at <https://doi.org/10.4236/jss.2025.132019>
- Nnebedum, C., Oshia, E.C., Nwanne, E.I., & Chinagorom, E.C. (2022). Principals' utilization of health committee and motivational technique as predictors of managerial effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. *Academic Journal of Current Research*, 9(11), 1-8.
- Obi, E., & Michael, I.E. (2024). Budgeting practices required by principals for effective administration of secondary schools in Anambra State. *Unizik Journal of Educational Management and Policy*, 6(2), 59-64.
- Obiekezie, N.P., & Obi, Z.C. (2025). ICT usage as a predictor of administrative effectiveness among principals of public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. *Nnadiabube Journal of Education in Africa*, 10(2), 36-43.
- Ofojebe W.N. and Ikegbunam, U.L. (2020). Roadmaps for effective administration of secondary education in Anambra State. *Unizik Journal of Educational Research and Policy Studies*, 14(1), 87-109.
- Okeke, I.N. and Okaforcha, C.C. (2020). Principals' auditing practices as predictors of teachers' job involvement in secondary schools in Anambra State. *African Journal of Educational Management, Teaching and Entrepreneurship Studies*, 1(1), 1-7.

- Okeze, W.O., Okpe, P.U., & Ngwakwe, E.J. (2018). Assessment of financial management practices of secondary schools in Abia State. *Journal of Economics and Environmental Education*, 3(1), 33-46.
- Onyali, L.C., Ogbo, R.N., & Uwaezuoke, M.I. (2023). Education law and principals' financial management practices for achieving Sustainable Developmental Goals in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. *Unizik Journal of Educational Management and Policy*, 5(2), 99-105.
- Oyeniran, S., Adebayo, M.A., Olayinka, O.F., & Tumburku, W.G. (2025). Principals' budget management practices and secondary school performance in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Sokoto Educational Review*, 24(1), 177-183.
- Thompson, C.C., Mmaduabuchi, B.C., Oparaji, I.C., & Chukwuemeka-Nworu, I.J. (2024). perceived impact of principals' financial management practices on secondary school administration in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State. *Unizik Journal of Educational Research and Policy Studies*, 18(1), 327-347.